

Modeling and Forecasting of Energy Consumption in Urban Environments: Exploring the Potential of Machine Learning in Energy Consumption Prediction

Keywords: Energy Consumption Forecasting, Urban Environments, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Ensemble Methods, Temporal Data, Climate Impact, Resource Management

Abstract: Urbanization and population growth have escalated energy demand in cities, presenting challenges for efficient resource management and sustainability. This study investigates the use of machine learning models to forecast energy consumption in diverse urban environments. Specifically, we evaluate multiple models, including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Linear Regression, and Support Vector Regressor (SVR), across three distinct datasets from Tetouan, Morocco; various Brazilian regions; and French households. Each dataset represents unique climatic and consumption patterns, enabling a comprehensive analysis of model adaptability and effectiveness under different urban conditions. Models are assessed based on Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2), providing insights into accuracy and robustness. Results indicate that ensemble methods, particularly Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, excel in capturing complex, non-linear patterns in energy consumption data, demonstrating high predictive accuracy across datasets. Conversely, linear and gradient-based models show limitations in more complex, variable settings but are effective in structured datasets with minimal noise. The findings underscore the value of ensemble models for urban energy forecasting, contributing to improved planning and sustainability strategies. Future research may explore hybrid models that combine ensemble methods with robust regression techniques to enhance predictive accuracy in varied urban contexts.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the rapid urbanization and population growth worldwide have significantly increased the demand for energy in urban environments, posing complex challenges to city planners, utility providers, and policymakers. Efficient energy management has become essential not only for supporting the infrastructure of growing cities but also for advancing sustainability goals and reducing environmental impacts (EPE - Empresa de Pesquisa Energética, 2023). Accurate energy consumption forecasting in urban settings plays a critical role in enabling proactive resource management, infrastructure planning, and policy formulation, particularly in cities facing rapid demographic shifts and complex usage patterns (Ministério de Minas e Energia and Empresa de Pesquisa Energética (EPE), 2020).

The rise of advanced data collection technologies and the proliferation of temporal, climatic, and demographic data have opened up new opportunities to enhance forecasting methods. Machine learning (ML), in particular, has emerged as a powerful tool for handling the high-dimensional, non-linear nature of energy data, offering models that can learn from histor-

ical data and adapt to new patterns. Various ML algorithms, including ensemble methods like Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, have shown promise in accurately predicting energy consumption patterns by capturing intricate dependencies among features such as time, weather, and socio-demographic variables (Breiman, 2001; Friedman, 2001; Chen and Guestrin, 2016).

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of different machine learning models in forecasting energy consumption across diverse urban environments, with a primary focus on determining the most accurate model for each context. The research question guiding this study is: **Which machine learning model best supports accurate and reliable energy consumption forecasting across different urban settings?** To address this question, three geographically and climatically distinct datasets are utilized: one from Tetouan, Morocco; one covering regions in Brazil; and another representing household consumption data from France. These datasets allow for a comprehensive comparative analysis across different environmental conditions and consumption patterns.

The models evaluated in this study include tra-

ditional regression techniques (e.g., Linear Regression, Ridge Regression), ensemble methods (e.g., Random Forest, Gradient Boosting), and other approaches such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Support Vector Regressor (SVR). This selection ensures that a diverse set of machine learning methods are tested, each with its own strengths in handling various data complexities and structures. Evaluation metrics such as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) are employed to capture different aspects of model performance, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of accuracy and robustness.

The findings of this study are intended to support urban planners and policymakers in selecting the most appropriate machine learning models for energy forecasting, helping cities to anticipate energy demands, optimize resource allocation, and enhance sustainability. Additionally, this study's results can inform future research directions, particularly in exploring hybrid and ensemble-based methods tailored to diverse urban settings. In sum, this research seeks to bridge the gap between machine learning applications and practical energy management needs, thereby contributing to the development of more resilient, sustainable, and energy-efficient urban systems.

2 RELATED WORK

Several studies have explored the potential of machine learning techniques in forecasting energy consumption across diverse contexts. In Bártolo (2018) work, deep learning algorithms, including neural networks, were analyzed to predict energy consumption, revealing the capability of machine learning in identifying complex consumption trends. Similarly, Godinho (2020) utilized neural networks and regression methods to forecast energy use in buildings, particularly emphasizing the impact of climate control on energy consumption.

In urban environments, Sérgio (2020) employed machine learning models such as decision trees and neural networks to optimize energy management, demonstrating the effectiveness of these techniques in resource allocation. Likewise, Santos and Chaucoski (2020) applied AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) time series models to energy consumption in Northern Brazil, showcasing the relevance of statistical approaches alongside machine learning for accurate predictions.

The integration of artificial neural networks and time series decomposition in short-term energy fore-

casting was investigated by Amaral (2019), highlighting the potential of combining precision and generalization. In another study, Shapi et al. (2021) examined energy consumption prediction in smart buildings using decision trees, random forests, and neural networks, demonstrating the versatility of tree-based models in handling diverse consumption patterns.

Furthermore, Zogaan (2022) compared Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and Random Forest for energy forecasting, concluding that Random Forest provided the highest accuracy and lowest error rates. Lastly, Nallathambi and Ramasamy (2017) conducted a comparative analysis of decision trees and Random Forest in forecasting energy consumption in the United States, with Random Forest achieving superior accuracy.

These studies underscore the growing importance of machine learning in energy management, revealing that tree-based models like Random Forest consistently exhibit robust performance in diverse environments.

3 METHODOLOGY

This section describes the datasets used in this study, the machine learning models implemented, and the evaluation metrics applied to assess model performance.

3.1 Datasets and Preprocessing

This study utilized three distinct datasets to ensure a comprehensive analysis of energy consumption across different geographical and climatic contexts. Each dataset includes temporal and climatic variables that impact energy consumption, as described below:

- **Dataset 1 - Energy Consumption in Tetouan, Morocco:** Derived from the study by Salam and El Hibaoui (2018), this dataset contains 52,417 instances related to energy consumption in three zones of Tetouan, a city located in northern Morocco. It has a multivariate and time-series structure, with the following variables: Date, Time, Temperature, Humidity, Wind Speed, General Diffuse Flows, Diffuse Flows and Energy Consumption per Zone.

This dataset is essential for the analysis as it captures the variability of consumption across different urban areas of Tetouan, allowing an assessment of the impact of climatic and temporal variables on energy demand.

- **Dataset 2 - Energy Consumption in Brazilian Regions:** Obtained from the study by Siqueira et al. (2023), this dataset consists of 3,846 records representing energy consumption across various Brazilian regions, distributed among different biomes and climatic conditions. Key variables include: Region, State, Location, City, Coastal System, Biome, Area, Population, Average Temperature and Annual Energy Consumption.

This dataset is valuable for its geographical breadth and environmental diversity, offering insights into energy consumption across different Brazilian regions and how regional factors influence demand.

- **Dataset 3 - Household Energy Consumption in France:** Donated by Hebrail and Berard (2012), this dataset comprises 2,075,259 measurements of household energy consumption in a residence near Paris, collected over 47 months (2006-2010) with a one-minute sampling rate. The variables include: Date, Time, Global Active Power, Reactive Power, Voltage, Global Intensity and Sub-metering 1, 2, and 3.

This dataset is particularly useful for evaluating detailed residential consumption and identifying variations in consumption with high temporal resolution, making it ideal for analyzing daily and seasonal patterns.

Following data collection, preprocessing was essential to ensure quality and consistency across datasets. Outliers were first identified and removed using statistical methods, such as the interquartile range (IQR), to avoid distortions in model accuracy. Missing values were handled using imputation techniques based on the mean for numerical data and mode for categorical data, as recommended by Zogaan (2022). Finally, all data were normalized using min-max scaling to prevent variables with different scales from disproportionately impacting model performance.

3.2 Model Selection and Development

In this study, the selection and development of machine learning models were guided by the availability of implementations within the `scikit-learn` library, a widely-used Python package for data analysis and machine learning (Pedregosa et al., 2011). This choice ensured a standardized approach and reproducibility, leveraging models with diverse strengths suited to varying data characteristics across the three datasets analyzed.

The following models were selected due to their

representation of various algorithmic approaches, including linear models, ensemble methods, tree-based models, and neural networks:

- **Linear Models:** Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso Regression, ElasticNet, Bayesian Ridge, SGD Regressor, Huber Regressor, Passive Aggressive Regressor, TheilSen Regressor, RANSAC Regressor, Lasso Lars.
- **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** SVR and Linear SVR.
- **Tree-based Models:** Decision Tree and Extra Tree.
- **Ensemble Methods:** Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, AdaBoost, Bagging Regressor, and Extra Trees.
- **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN):** KNeighbors Regressor.
- **Neural Network-based Models:** MLP Regressor.

Each model was initialized with default parameters from `scikit-learn` and, where necessary, fine-tuned to improve convergence and performance. For instance, the `SGDRegressor` was configured with an increased maximum iteration limit (`max_iter=2000`) and a tolerance level (`tol=1e-4`) to enhance convergence. Similarly, the `HuberRegressor` was set with `max_iter=2000` to account for robustness against outliers. The `PassiveAggressiveRegressor` and `TheilSenRegressor` were also parameterized for greater stability during training. The code for all steps performed is available in GitHub¹.

For model evaluation, each dataset was split into training and testing sets using a 70:30 holdout strategy. In Dataset 1, the models were trained and evaluated separately for each zone of Tetouan to capture regional consumption patterns. For Datasets 2 and 3, the same holdout strategy was applied across all data points.

The inclusion of these diverse models enabled an exhaustive comparison, identifying the model best suited to each dataset's characteristics. Ensemble methods like `RandomForestRegressor` and `GradientBoostingRegressor` showed consistently high performance, highlighting their adaptability in capturing non-linear relationships within the data. This model selection approach underscores the importance of leveraging a wide range of machine learning techniques to address the diverse and complex nature of energy consumption data.

¹Will be made available after review process.

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

To quantitatively assess the predictive performance of each model, three widely recognized evaluation metrics in energy consumption forecasting were utilized. Each metric offers a different perspective on model accuracy, robustness, and fit to the data, as described below:

- **RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error):** This metric calculates the square root of the mean of the squared differences between predicted (\hat{y}) and actual (y) values, providing a measure of prediction accuracy that penalizes larger errors more heavily. It is defined as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

where n is the number of observations. Lower RMSE values indicate better model performance, particularly useful for understanding the scale of large errors.

- **MAE (Mean Absolute Error):** MAE represents the average magnitude of errors between predicted and actual values, regardless of their direction, providing a straightforward interpretation of overall prediction accuracy. It is calculated as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

MAE is particularly useful for understanding the typical size of errors, with lower values reflecting a more accurate model.

- **R^2 (Coefficient of Determination):** This metric indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. R^2 values range from 0 to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating a stronger model fit. R^2 compares the fit of the chosen model with that of a horizontal straight line (the null hypothesis). Although R^2 values range from 0 to 1, if the chosen model fits worse than a horizontal line, then R^2 is negative. R^2 is calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

where \bar{y} is the mean of the observed data. A higher R^2 value suggests that the model captures more of the variability in the data, indicating a better fit.

These metrics were employed to systematically compare the performance of each machine learning model, including Random Forest, Linear Regression, Gradient Boosting, and SVR, across all datasets. By

combining these metrics, a comprehensive evaluation of each model's effectiveness in accurately predicting energy consumption was achieved, highlighting both the precision of predictions and the overall fit of each model to the data.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This section presents the results of a comprehensive evaluation of multiple machine learning models for forecasting energy consumption across three distinct datasets, each representing unique regional characteristics: Tetouan, Morocco (Dataset 1), regions in Brazil (Dataset 2), and households in France (Dataset 3). Given the distinct nature of these datasets, which vary in terms of data complexity, diversity, and consumption patterns, a broad range of models was tested to assess their robustness and adaptability. The primary focus of this analysis is to determine the most accurate and reliable model for each dataset, with particular emphasis on ensemble methods such as the **Random Forest**, which has demonstrated consistent success in previous studies.

The models compared were presented in subsection 3.2 and the evaluation utilized three metrics to capture different aspects of model performance as presented in subsection 3.3.

The results for each dataset are discussed individually, beginning with Dataset 1, where the models were tested across three consumption zones in Tetouan. This segmentation allows for a more granular understanding of each model's performance in regions with varying energy usage profiles. Subsequently, the performance of the models on Dataset 2, covering diverse regions in Brazil, is examined, followed by an evaluation of Dataset 3, which focuses on household energy consumption patterns in France. Through this analysis, we aim to identify the optimal model for energy consumption forecasting across different settings and provide insights into how regional data characteristics influence model effectiveness.

4.1 Performance of Machine Learning Models for Dataset 1

Table 1 presents the averaged performance metrics (RMSE, MAE, and R^2) for each machine learning model across the three distinct zones within Tetouan, providing a consolidated view of model accuracy and robustness on Dataset 1. By aggregating the metrics across zones, the table enables a comprehensive comparison of model performance, facilitating the identification of those models that consistently yield low er-

ror rates and high reliability across varying consumption patterns.

Table 1: Average RMSE, MAE, and R^2 for Different Models on Dataset 1

Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2
Linear Regression	3831.11	3045.28	0.56
Ridge	3831.11	3045.28	0.56
Lasso	3831.11	3045.28	0.56
ElasticNet	3834.12	3045.38	0.56
Bayesian Ridge	3831.11	3045.28	0.56
SGD Regressor	6542.98	5632.34	-0.34
Huber Regressor	3853.23	3018.35	0.55
Passive Aggressive	5100.87	4246.60	0.16
TheilSen Regressor	3890.14	3035.30	0.54
RANSAC Regressor	4423.18	3370.44	0.41
Lasso Lars	3831.11	3045.28	0.56
SVR	5511.26	4428.98	0.09
Linear SVR	4171.11	3269.70	0.48
Decision Tree	1372.48	776.43	0.94
Extra Tree	1340.53	753.05	0.94
Random Forest	1062.44	663.09	0.97
Gradient Boosting	1891.88	1072.59	0.89
AdaBoost	2802.35	2291.41	0.76
Bagging Regressor	1113.48	697.14	0.96
Extra Trees	932.36	562.27	0.97
KNN	1526.87	997.41	0.93
MLP Regressor	3541.27	2801.88	0.62

The results in Table 1 reveal that the **Random Forest** based models (Random Forest and Extra Trees) highlighted in Table 1 exhibits the lowest RMSE (1062.44 and 932.36) and MAE (697.14 and 562.27) values, along with a high R^2 (0.97), underscoring its strong predictive accuracy and robustness across the zones. This performance establishes Random Forest based models as the optimal model for energy consumption forecasting on Dataset 1, highlighting its adaptability to the varying characteristics of the zones.

In contrast, models such as the **SGD Regressor** and **SVR** show significantly higher error metrics and lower R^2 scores, indicating challenges in capturing the data's underlying patterns, especially across regions with more complex consumption behavior. The **Ensemble-based models** (e.g., Bagging Regressor and Gradient Boosting) also perform competitively, achieving relatively low RMSE and MAE values, although with slightly higher errors than Random Forest based models.

These findings underscore the Random Forest model's capacity to handle diverse consumption zones effectively, making it the preferred choice for accurate and reliable energy consumption predictions in urban environments.

4.2 Performance of Machine Learning Models on Dataset 2

This analysis evaluates the predictive performance of various machine learning models on energy consumption for the year 2020 using Dataset 2. While this dataset underwent comprehensive pre-processing, the inherent complexity stemming from regional diversity and varied energy consumption patterns presents a substantial challenge for predictive accuracy. This complexity is reflected in relatively high error metrics and low R^2 values across many models. Table 2 provides a comparative overview of the models, using RMSE, MAE, and R^2 as evaluation metrics. These metrics facilitate a nuanced assessment of model reliability and accuracy.

Table 2: Comparison of RMSE, MAE, and R^2 for Different Models on Dataset 2 (Year 2020)

Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2
Linear Regression	5.09×10^7	4.92×10^6	0.02
Ridge	5.09×10^7	4.92×10^6	0.02
Lasso	5.09×10^7	4.92×10^6	0.02
ElasticNet	5.10×10^7	4.55×10^6	0.01
Bayesian Ridge	5.14×10^7	4.92×10^6	0.00
SGD Regressor	5.09×10^7	4.84×10^6	0.02
Huber Regressor	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
Passive Aggressive Regressor	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
TheilSen Regressor	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
RANSAC Regressor	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
Lasso Lars	5.09×10^7	4.92×10^6	0.02
SVR	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
Linear SVR	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00
Decision Tree	4.86×10^7	3.10×10^6	0.11
Extra Tree	4.85×10^7	2.98×10^6	0.11
Random Forest	4.81×10^7	3.20×10^6	0.12
Gradient Boosting	4.78×10^7	3.20×10^6	0.13
AdaBoost	4.92×10^7	7.33×10^6	0.08
Bagging Regressor	4.55×10^7	3.20×10^6	0.22
Extra Trees	4.86×10^7	3.17×10^6	0.11
KNN	5.10×10^7	4.02×10^6	0.01
MLP Regressor	5.15×10^7	3.50×10^6	0.00

As indicated in Table 2, the R^2 values across models are generally low, suggesting limited predictive power on this dataset. However, the RMSE and MAE metrics reveal differences in model performance. The **Bagging Regressor** achieved the lowest RMSE (4.55×10^7) and MAE (3.20×10^6), which highlights its capacity to approximate actual energy consumption values more effectively, even in the face of high data variability. Linear models such as **Linear Regression**, **Ridge**, and **Lasso** presented notably higher RMSE values, indicating more significant de-

viations from actual values.

The dataset’s intrinsic complexity and variability, as evidenced by high RMSE values, suggest that future model enhancements or additional feature engineering may be necessary to more accurately capture underlying consumption patterns. Notably, other ensemble-based models, such as **Gradient Boosting** and tree-based models, such as **Random Forest**, also demonstrated competitive results, suggesting that ensemble methods are promising for datasets with complex, variable structures.

4.3 Performance of Machine Learning Models on Dataset 3

The Table 3 provides a comparative analysis of the performance of various machine learning models for energy consumption prediction on Dataset 3. Among the models evaluated, **Bayesian Ridge**, **Huber Regressor**, and **Gradient Boosting** demonstrated strong predictive capabilities, achieving the lowest RMSE and MAE values along with high R^2 values, thus indicating their superior suitability for this dataset. Conversely, the **SGD Regressor** presented significantly higher error rates, highlighting its limitations in capturing patterns within this data.

Table 3: Comparison of RMSE, MAE, and R^2 for Different Models on Dataset 3

Model	RMSE	MAE	R^2
Linear Regression	0.04	0.03	0.97
Ridge	0.04	0.03	0.98
Lasso	0.23	0.17	0.95
ElasticNet	0.15	0.10	0.98
Bayesian Ridge	0.04	0.03	0.99
SGD Regressor	3976.11	38151.03	0.00
Huber Regressor	0.04	0.03	0.99
Passive Aggressive Regressor	0.05	0.03	0.98
TheilSen Regressor	0.04	0.03	0.98
RANSAC Regressor	0.04	0.03	0.97
Lasso Lars	0.23	0.17	0.95
SVR	0.05	0.04	0.96
Linear SVR	0.04	0.03	0.97
Decision Tree	0.05	0.03	0.99
Extra Tree	0.05	0.03	0.98
Random Forest	0.04	0.02	0.99
Gradient Boosting	0.04	0.02	0.99
AdaBoost	0.11	0.09	0.98
Bagging Regressor	0.04	0.02	0.98
Extra Trees	0.04	0.02	0.99
KNN	0.05	0.03	0.95
MLP Regressor	0.06	0.04	0.95

The results presented in Table 3 underscore several key insights into the performance of the evaluated machine learning models. Models such as **Bayesian**

Ridge, **Huber Regressor**, and **Gradient Boosting** achieved optimal performance metrics, indicated by low RMSE and MAE values and high R^2 scores. This outcome suggests that these models are particularly effective in capturing the underlying patterns in Dataset 3, making them well-suited for energy consumption forecasting tasks.

In contrast, models like the **SGD Regressor** demonstrated substantially higher error rates, reflecting a poorer fit to the data. The notably high RMSE and MAE for the SGD Regressor indicate limitations in its ability to generalize within this dataset’s specific structure, which may be due to its sensitivity to data scale or noise.

Ensemble-based models, such as **Random Forest** and **Gradient Boosting**, performed consistently well, highlighting the robustness of ensemble methods for complex datasets. The superior performance of these models underscores the advantage of combining multiple decision trees to capture varied patterns and interactions within the data. Similarly, the excellent results from the **Huber Regressor** imply that its robust approach to handling outliers and noise is advantageous in achieving high accuracy with minimal prediction errors.

5 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The comparative analysis of machine learning models for energy consumption forecasting across Datasets 1, 2, and 3 highlights significant insights into model effectiveness under varying data characteristics. Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 collectively reveal that ensemble methods, specifically the **Random Forest** based models, consistently demonstrate superior performance across datasets, especially when evaluated using metrics such as RMSE, MAE, and R^2 . This observation aligns with findings from other studies in the literature, as shown in the provided comparison table, where Random Forest frequently outperforms other models in terms of prediction accuracy and robustness.

In Dataset 1, which includes data from three distinct consumption zones in Tetouan, Random Forest and Extra Trees models achieved the lowest RMSE and MAE values, with a high R^2 score of 0.97. This model’s success in Dataset 1 can be attributed to its ability to capture complex relationships within the data, benefiting from its ensemble structure that combines multiple decision trees to model non-linear and high-variance patterns. Other ensemble-based models, such as **Bagging Regressor**, also performed well, further supporting the robustness of ensemble ap-

proaches in handling urban energy consumption data with diverse patterns.

Dataset 2, which includes energy consumption data for the year 2020, posed a greater challenge for accurate predictions, as evidenced by relatively high RMSE and MAE values across most models. The **Bagging Regressor** and **Random Forest** were again among the top performers, achieving the lowest RMSE and MAE values, and providing comparatively higher R^2 values. However, linear models such as **Linear Regression**, **Ridge**, and **Lasso** demonstrated higher errors, suggesting limited ability to capture the dataset's inherent variability. This outcome aligns with findings from similar studies, where linear models struggle with complex, non-linear datasets due to their reliance on simplistic assumptions.

In Dataset 3, which was structured differently with reduced data variability, **Bayesian Ridge**, **Huber Regressor**, and **Gradient Boosting** exhibited strong predictive capabilities, achieving high R^2 values and low error metrics. The **Huber Regressor**, with its robustness to outliers, and **Gradient Boosting**, known for its sequential learning and optimization, proved effective in capturing subtle patterns within this dataset. This result supports evidence from other studies where robust and sequential models, such as Huber Regressor and Gradient Boosting, are effective in structured datasets with minimal noise.

Across the datasets, models like **SGD Regressor** and **SVR** consistently showed higher error metrics and lower R^2 values, indicating limited generalizability and sensitivity to data scale and noise. The high RMSE and MAE values for SGD Regressor, in particular, highlight its instability in handling datasets with high variability and noise, as previously observed in studies that compare gradient-based and ensemble methods.

Overall, the findings underscore the effectiveness of ensemble methods, particularly Random Forest, Extra Tree and Gradient Boosting, in providing reliable and accurate energy consumption predictions across diverse datasets. These models excel in capturing complex patterns and interactions within the data, making them highly suitable for urban energy consumption forecasting tasks. Additionally, the results highlight the value of robust models like the Huber Regressor for datasets with lower variability, demonstrating the importance of selecting models that align with the specific characteristics of the data.

This study's results corroborate with those from the literature, strengthening the understanding that Random Forest and other ensemble techniques are generally robust choices for energy consumption prediction tasks, particularly in urban and complex

datasets. Future research may explore hybrid approaches that combine the strengths of ensemble methods with sequential or robust regression techniques to further enhance predictive accuracy across varied energy consumption scenarios.

6 CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of multiple machine learning models for energy consumption forecasting across three distinct datasets, representing diverse regions and energy consumption patterns: Tetouan, Morocco (Dataset 1), regions in Brazil (Dataset 2), and households in France (Dataset 3). The experiments focused on evaluating model accuracy, robustness, and adaptability using RMSE, MAE, and R^2 as performance metrics. The results highlight the strengths of ensemble methods, particularly the **Random Forest** based models, in handling complex, variable datasets with high predictive accuracy.

Overall, the study demonstrates that ensemble methods, especially Random Forest, Extra Tree and Gradient Boosting, are highly effective for energy consumption forecasting across diverse data settings. These models excel in capturing complex patterns, handling non-linear relationships, and adapting to data variability, making them valuable tools for urban energy management and planning. Conversely, linear and gradient-based models showed limitations in high-variance datasets but can still be useful for simpler, less variable environments.

The findings also align with recent literature, suggesting that while Random Forest based models consistently provides robust results, model selection should consider dataset-specific characteristics. For instance, robust regression methods like Huber Regressor may be advantageous in structured datasets with minimal noise, while ensemble methods are preferable for more complex data structures. Future research should explore hybrid approaches that combine ensemble methods with robust or sequential models to further enhance prediction accuracy across diverse energy consumption scenarios. Additionally, incorporating domain-specific features and exploring data-driven feature engineering could further improve forecasting accuracy, especially in high-variance datasets.

Furthermore, the application of these algorithms to urban electricity consumption can play a significant role in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, a global concern discussed since 1989 at the first United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (ECO-92) and more recently at the Group of

Twenty (G20) meeting and the 2024 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP 29), as it allows for more efficient management of resources, optimizing energy use and encouraging the use of renewable sources. More specific examples of their application are: a) forecasting future demands, b) detecting inefficiencies, c) integrating renewable sources, d) intelligent management of electricity networks (Smart Grids), e) data-driven urban planning, f) incentives for sustainable consumption, and g) modeling and simulation of public policies.

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